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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Analyzes internalized aesthetic pressures among gay men, exploring how unrealistic body ideals impact mental health, self-esteem, and intimacy. Discusses processes of deconstructing oppressive patterns and cultivating authentic body acceptance. Offers therapeutic interventions to challenge toxic comparison and internalized objectification, promoting healthier relationships with the body and emancipated sexuality.

Keywords

shame, identity, mental health

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